

Cultural Extinction under Climate Change: Threats to the Indigenous Use of Giant Conifers in Northern Forests

Kobayashi MAKOTO

The affiliation and address of (corresponding) author: Field Science Center for Northern Biosphere, Hokkaido University, Tokuda 250, Nayoro, Hokkaido 096-0071, Japan

***Corresponding author:** Kobayashi MAKOTO, The affiliation and address of (corresponding) author: Field Science Center for Northern Biosphere, Hokkaido University, Tokuda 250, Nayoro, Hokkaido 096-0071, Japan, Tel: +81-1632-6-5211; E-mail: makoto.baobab@gmail.com

Abstract

Boreal and northern temperate forests are home to northern indigenous peoples, and large conifers are vital to their lives. However, under climate warming, large coniferous trees are declining in these northern forests, which may threaten the way of life for northern indigenous peoples, who rely on large coniferous trees. It takes several centuries for coniferous trees to become large. The disappearance of giant conifers causes indigenous people to lose traditional knowledge about the use of these trees in their traditional ways, a loss that will inevitably become permanent over several centuries.

Furthermore, the “extinction of experience” of being in front of these giant trees might create negative feedback for indigenous societies by eliminating their recognition of the importance of such trees for their culture, so they may put less effort into conserving the giant conifers of boreal and temperate forests.

In addition to conserving giant conifers themselves, we should also address the parallel goal of creating experiences that introduce people to giant conifers via ecological education or nature tourism. The protection of these giant trees can provide an interface between the mitigation of global climate change and the conservation of local cultural services provided to indigenous people in boreal and northern temperate regions.

Mini Review

The importance of cultural ecosystem services has been recognized within the framework of ecosystem services (Daniel et al. 2012). Because of its importance, causes and the consequence of cultural extinction in human society has been attracting the attention of scientists. However, the pathways via which climate change drives cultural extinction has little recognized. In this Perspective, I would like to advocate a pathway how the climate change potentially causes cultural extinction of northern indigenous people via the decline of giant coniferous trees.

The boreal and northern temperate forests are broadly covered by coniferous trees. In addition to supplying significant provisional (e.g., timber production) and regulating services (e.g., carbon stock), coniferous forests play essential roles as the homes of northern indigenous peoples (Gauthier et al. 2015). The current value of the Canadian boreal

forest for indigenous people in terms of subsistence foods is nearly 600 million dollars (Karst 2010). With respect to the characteristic uses of boreal forests by northern indigenous people, for example, the Sami people in Scandinavia use arboreal lichen (such as *Bryoria fuscescens*) and inner bark in Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) forest for their reindeer husbandry and food resources (Horstkotte et al. 2011). On the northwest coast of north America (where is the ecotone between temperate and boreal forests), the Tlingit people use western redcedar (*Thuja plicata*) for many purposes such as for making lodges, canoes and totem poles, and baskets (Johnson et al. 2021). Importantly among the coniferous trees, large individuals are vital to northern indigenous peoples as materials for traditional construction. For example, the Tlingit, Haida and Tsimshian in Alaska use large western redcedar to construct totem pole, canoe and longhouse (Johnson et al. 2021) (Figure 1a). Similarly, the Ainu people of the island of Hokkaido in northern Japan use the giant trunks of broad-leaved trees as well as conifers to make traditional ocean-going boats (“Itaomachipu”, Figure 1b). In both cases, the trees suitable for such large construction should generally be more than a few to several hundred years old to be the correct size (e.g., Yajima & Matsuda 1978).

Figure 1: Conceptual relationship between giant coniferous trees and traditional constructions such as (a) totem poles in Canada and (b) ocean-going boats in northern Japan. The giant coniferous trees can be used for the traditional construction with the aid of traditional knowledge about the usage of giant coniferous trees by indigenous people (c). By identifying the value of traditional construction, the motivation to conserve giant coniferous trees can be activated.

Under climate warming, however, the coniferous trees have been declining. In Alaska and northern Japan, tree-ring analysis and long-term monitoring has indicated that the decline of conifers is driven by temperature-induced drought stress (Barber et al. 2000; Hiura et al. 2019). Regrettably, larger conifers are especially sensitive to drought stress (Bennett et al. 2015). The decline of large conifers may threaten northern indigenous peoples’ way of life. This is due to the loss of both the materials suitable for traditional large construction and the opportunity to use traditional knowledge to utilize the cultural ecosystem services provided by giant conifers (Díaz 2015) (Figure 1). Moreover, it

takes several centuries for coniferous trees to become large, and the disappearance of these giant trees causes indigenous people to lose traditional knowledge about their use over several centuries.

Another concern is that modern urban people who have less experience with nature will have less interest in its conservation (Soga & Gaston 2016). The “extinction of experience” of being in front of the giant trees might create a negative feedback for indigenous societies by eliminating their recognition of the importance of such trees for their culture, so they may put less effort into conserving the giant conifers of boreal and temperate forests. In fact, lower levels of neighbourhood tree cover are associated with a reduced frequency of visits to forests (Gaston & Soga 2020), although the specific importance with large tree is poorly understood. To mitigate these changes to safeguard indigenous culture and lifestyle, we should reacknowledge the irreplaceable cultural value of the giant coniferous trees and their products, not only to conserve giant conifers themselves but also to create experiences that introduce people to these trees via ecological education or nature tourism and motivate people to conserve them (Figure 1). For the conservation of giant conifers, for example, the existing database about the distribution of giant trees (e.g., Nakadai 2023) as well as the technique of detecting giant trees with remote sensing together with deep learning algorithms (Lang et al. 2023) would be useful. The protection of these large trees can provide an interface between the mitigation of global climate change and the conservation of local cultural ecosystem services provided to indigenous people in boreal and northern temperate regions.

Ethical Statement

The Copyright of the photos: the Society for Academic Research of Ainu Culture. (The author got permission from the Society for Academic Research of Ainu Culture to use the attached figure for the scientific publication)

Acknowledgement

I sincerely thank the Society for Academic Research of Ainu Culture and Mr. Tokuhei Narita for giving me the opportunity to interview about this topic. I appreciate Ms. Natsuko Kasai for providing a photo of totem pole in Canada and Drs. Russell Kramer, Michael Jonsson and Scott D. Wilson during the preparation of this manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

1. Barber VA, Juday GP, Finney BP. 2000. Reduced growth of Alaskan white spruce in the twentieth century from temperature-induced drought stress. *Nature* 405:668–673.
2. Bennett AC, Mcdowell NG, Allen CD, Anderson-Teixeira KJ. 2015. Larger trees suffer most during drought in forests worldwide. *Nature Plants* 1.
3. Daniel TC et al. 2012. Contributions of cultural services to the ecosystem services agenda. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 109:8812–8819.
4. Díaz S et al. 2015. The IPBES Conceptual Framework — connecting nature and people. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* 14:1–16.

5. Gaston KJ, Soga M. 2020. Extinction of experience: The need to be more specific. *People and Nature* 2:575–581.
6. Gauthier S, Bernier P, Kuuluvainen T, Shvidenko AZ, Schepaschenko DG. 2015. Boreal forest health and global change. *Science* 349:819–822.
7. Hiura T, Go S, Iijima H. 2019. Long-term forest dynamics in response to climate change in northern mixed forests in Japan: A 38-year individual-based approach. *Forest Ecology and Management* 449:117469. Elsevier. Available from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2019.117469>.
8. Horstkotte T, Moen J, Lämås T, Helle T. 2011. The legacy of logging-estimating arboreal lichen occurrence in a boreal multiple-use landscape on a two century scale. *PLoS ONE* 6.
9. Johnson A et al. 2021. Wood products for cultural uses: Sustaining native resilience and vital lifeways in southeast Alaska, USA. *Forests* 12:1–26.
10. Karst A. 2010. Conservation Value of the North American Boreal Forest from an Ethnobotanical Perspective. Ottawa, ON; Vancouver, BC; Seattle, WA.
11. Lang N, Jetz W, Schindler K, Wegner JD. 2023. A high-resolution canopy height model of the Earth. *Nature Ecology and Evolution* 7:1778–1789. Springer US.
12. Nakadai R. 2023. Macroecological processes drive spiritual ecosystem services obtained from giant trees. *Nature Plants* 9:209–213. Springer US.
13. Soga M, Gaston KJ. 2016. Extinction of experience: The loss of human-nature interactions. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 14:94–101.
14. Yajima T, Matsuda K. 1978. Growth of main tree species in the mixed forest of the northern Hokkaido. *Research Bulletin of the Hokkaido University Forests* 35:29–63.